

EVALUATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF SELF-EFFICACY, ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND INTERNSHIP ON WORK READINESS OF CIVIL ENGINEERING DIPLOMA STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of self-efficacy, academic achievement, and internship experience on the work readiness of Civil Engineering D4 students, class of 2019-2021 at Surabaya State University. The sample in this study was all 166 students. Using multiple linear regression analysis, the results of the study showed that self-efficacy had a positive and significant effect on work readiness, with a significance value of 0.000 and a regression coefficient of 0.431. This shows that increasing self-confidence contributes to readiness to face the world of work. On the other hand, academic achievement did not show a significant effect with a significance value of 0.161. Internship experience, although it has a negative regression coefficient of -0.122, is proven to have a significant effect on work readiness with a significance value of 0.021, this shows the importance of the relevance of internship experience.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Academic Performance, Internship, Work Readiness.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, all sectors, including education, are expected to continue to improve their competence to produce quality human resources (HR) who are ready to face the world of work. Universities have an important role as a place for intellectuals to contribute to accelerating progress in the economic, social, cultural, and technological fields. Ideally, universities not only produce graduates with academic knowledge, but also with professional skills (Rukiyanto et al., 2023). With these skills, it is hoped that they can develop the creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurial spirit needed to face global challenges (Marlinah, 2019).

Student work readiness is one of the central issues in facing the challenges of an increasingly competitive global labor market (Telaumbanua & Telaumbanua, 2024). Not only a concern for individuals, work readiness is also a major focus for educational institutions and the industrial world. Universities, in particular, have a responsibility to produce graduates who are not only academically competent but also have the skills and mentality to work in a stressful and rapidly changing environment (maryam, 2023) In various developed countries, such as the UK, higher education has a strategic mission to create national competitiveness through the development of work-ready graduates, which ultimately also has a positive impact on economic growth.

Therefore, student work readiness is not only important for the graduates themselves, but also for companies and society in general, because a ready workforce will be able to increase productivity and more optimal work results (Irfan et al., 2023).

The first factor that plays a role in students' work readiness is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their ability to plan, organize, and carry out the actions needed to achieve certain goals (Sagala et al., 2024). Individuals with high self-efficacy will be more optimistic and confident in facing the various challenges and obstacles they encounter, including in the workplace. In the context of work readiness, students who have high self-efficacy tend to be better able to navigate the demands of a complex work environment, both in terms of adapting to new environments, solving problems creatively, and communicating effectively in teams (Aprilita, 2024). Students with good self-efficacy will not only be more confident in overcoming challenges in the workplace, but also more resilient when faced with failure or difficulties (Mufidah, 2017).

The second factor that plays an important role is academic performance. Academic performance describes the extent to which students are able to understand and master the academic material taught in class, and how they apply that knowledge (Cahyono & Gunawan, 2024). Students with good academic achievement usually have critical, analytical, and systematic thinking skills that are very important in the workplace. They have been trained to solve problems logically and in a structured manner, and have the discipline to complete the tasks given. Previous research shows that students with good academic performance are better able to face complex work demands, because they have been accustomed to working with high standards during the lecture process (Lucas et al., 2017). In other words, good academic achievement is an important indicator of students' readiness to enter the workforce, because they already have a strong foundation of knowledge and skills (Hulwani & Aliyyah, 2024).

As the demands of the workplace increase, academics are increasingly aware of the importance of developing students' knowledge and skills so that they are ready to compete in the job market. Today, employers are not only looking for graduates who have the technical skills and knowledge needed, but also individuals who have a proactive attitude, a desire to learn, and the ability to adapt quickly (Dewi et al., 2024)

Technical skills alone are not enough; employers also want graduates who have good communication skills, critical thinking skills, effective problem-solving skills, and the ability to work in a team (Dewi et al., 2024). In addition, flexibility is a highly valued quality in facing a constantly changing work environment. This combination of technical and interpersonal skills is essential to help graduates not only meet the needs of today's workplace, but also thrive in facing the challenges of the industrial revolution 4.0 era (P Sumampouw & Mandey, n.d.). In this context, the balance between hard skills and soft skills is the key to optimal work readiness (Lestari & Arini, 2024).

The third factor that plays a significant role in students' work readiness is internship experience. Internship experience provides students with the opportunity to apply the theories learned in class to real-world situations in the (Mufidatul et al., 2024). Through internships, students can

develop practical skills needed by the industry, such as technical skills, understanding of work processes, and soft skills such as communication and teamwork. Internships also allow students to understand the dynamics of the work world, including work ethic, company culture, and performance expectations (Lestari & Arini, 2024). Students who have undergone internships tend to have higher work readiness because they have interacted directly with the professional environment and know what is expected of them when entering the workforce (Valentina, n.d.). In addition, internships also help students build professional networks that can support their future careers, as well as provide them with insight into the career paths they may choose after graduation (Aksa, 2023).

By considering these three factors, self-efficacy, academic performance, and internship experience. This study aims to analyze the influence of each factor on students' work readiness. Through a deeper understanding of how these factors affect work readiness, it is hoped that the results of this study can provide practical recommendations for educational institutions in designing more comprehensive and integrated learning programs. Thus, educational institutions can be more effective in preparing graduates who not only have strong academic knowledge, but also the skills and confidence needed to succeed in the world of work, so that they are able to compete in the global job market.

2. METHOD

This type of research is quantitative research because the data collected is in the form of numbers and analyzed using statistics. The method used is descriptive and verification methods, with an ex post facto approach and survey without sample in the study was all 166 students.

The descriptive method aims to describe and interpret the research object based on existing reality, without any exaggeration. Meanwhile, the verification method is used to see the influence between the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). The ex post facto approach is used because the data collected is based on conditions that already exist at the research site. While surveys are used to collect data from the natural environment (not artificial), for example through questionnaires, interviews, or observations.

Figure 1: Research Framework

Research hypothesis :

Ha1: Self-efficacy variable has an effect on work readiness

Ha2: Academic performance variables have an effect on work readiness

Ha3: Internship variables have an effect on work readiness

Ha4: The variables of academic performance, self-efficacy, and internships have an effect on work readiness.

Data collection techniques in this study consisted of three main methods: observation, questionnaires, and documentation. Observations were conducted to understand the influence of work readiness on Civil Engineering D4 students in the 2019-2021 intake at Surabaya State University. Through observation, researchers can directly observe the behavior and conditions of students related to their work readiness. Questionnaires were used to collect data on self-efficacy, academic performance, internship experience, and work readiness of Civil Engineering students in the 2019-2021 intake. This questionnaire functions as an instrument to measure students' perceptions and attitudes towards the variables studied. Documentation aims to obtain data in the form of books, archives, documents, and other information that supports this study, including reports and images related to students' work readiness. Documentation helps complete information from primary data collected through observation and questionnaires. In this study, all questionnaires used have been proven valid and reliable. Validity tests were conducted to ensure that the instruments measure appropriately according to the research objectives, using SPSS software with the Product Moment correlation technique. Meanwhile, reliability tests ensure the consistency of measurement results using the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient..

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Normality Test

The normality test is conducted to evaluate whether the residuals obtained from the study have a normal distribution or not. If the significance value is greater than 0.05, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. Based on the table below, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov significance value shows a figure of 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the residuals are normally distributed.

Table 1: Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.200 ^c

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity testing is performed in multiple regression analysis involving more than one independent variable (Sriningsih et al., n.d.). To detect multicollinearity, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) indicator is used. If the VIF value for each variable is less than 10 and the tolerance value is more than 0.1, it can be concluded that the multiple linear regression model does not

experience multicollinearity problems.

Table 2: Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
X1	.968	1.033
X2	.493	2.029
X3	.495	2.020

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the self-efficacy variable has a tolerance value of 0.968 and a VIF value of 1.033. The academic performance variable has a tolerance value of 0.493 and a VIF value of 2.029, and the internship variable has a tolerance value of 0.495 and a VIF value of 2.020. All variables have a tolerance value of more than 0.1 and a VIF value of less than 10, so the conclusion is that the multiple regression model is free from multicollinearity and the assumption of non-multicollinearity is met.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is conducted to assess whether there is inconsistent variability in the absolute value of the residuals from the regression related to independent variables, such as self-efficacy, work motivation, and internship experience (Aliudin & Adi Chandra Damora, 2024). The results of this test are considered significant if the value is more than 0.05, which indicates that there is no heteroscedasticity problem; conversely, if the value is below 0.05, heteroscedasticity can be considered to exist. The following are the results of the heteroscedasticity test using the Glejser method:

Table 3: Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Model	Sig.
self efficacy	.555
academic performance	.803
apprenticeship	.212

From the table above, it is known that the significance figures of the three independent variables in this study have values greater than 0.05, namely the self-efficacy variable of 0.555, the academic performance variable of 0.803, and the internship variable of 0.212, which concludes that there is no heteroscedasticity, so the assumption of heteroscedasticity can be met

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Table 4: Multiple Linear Test Results

Model	B
(Constant)	8.046
Self Efficacy	.431
academic performance	-2.360
apprenticeship	-.122

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the constant value (α value) is 8.046 and for Self-Efficacy (β value) is 0.431 while Academic Performance (β value) is -2.360 and Internship (β

value) is -0.122. So that the multiple linear regression equation can be obtained as follows:

$$Y = 8,046 + 0,431X1 - 2,360X2 - 0,122X3 + e$$

Based on the results obtained, it can be explained as follows:

Constant (8.046): If the variables of self-efficacy, academic performance, and internship experience are all zero, then work readiness is predicted to be 8.046. This means that there are other factors outside the model that influence work readiness.

Self-Efficacy Coefficient ($X1 = 0.431$): Every one unit increase in self-efficacy will increase work readiness by 0.431, assuming other variables remain constant. This shows that self-efficacy has a positive effect on work readiness; the higher a person's self-confidence, the more prepared they are to enter the work readiness.

Academic Performance Coefficient ($X2 = -2.360$): Every one unit increase in academic performance actually decreases job readiness by 2.360, assuming other variables remain constant. This may indicate that high academic performance does not necessarily reflect job readiness, and that students with an academic focus may lack the practical skills needed in the work readiness.

Academic Performance Coefficient ($X2 = -2.360$): Every one unit increase in academic performance actually decreases job readiness by 2.360, assuming other variables remain constant. This may indicate that high academic performance does not necessarily reflect job readiness, and students with an academic focus may lack the practical skills needed in the work readiness.

Internship Experience Coefficient ($X3 = -0.122$): Each one-unit increase in internship experience reduces job readiness by 0.122, assuming other variables remain constant. This small negative effect may indicate that internship experience gained is not yet relevant or has little significant impact on job readiness.

t-Test (Partial)

The t-test is conducted to assess the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable partially.

Table 5: t-Test Results (Partial)

Model	Sig.
Self Efficacy	.000
Academic Performance	.161
Apprenticeship	.021

Based on the results of the partial t-test, it was found that the self-efficacy variable has a significance value of 0.000, which indicates that its influence on students' work readiness is statistically significant. This means that self-efficacy makes a real contribution to work readiness, where students with higher levels of self-efficacy tend to feel more prepared to face the world of work.

On the other hand, the academic performance variable has a significance value of 0.161, which means that its influence is not statistically significant on work readiness. In other words, academic performance does not have a significant impact on influencing students' readiness to work. Although academic achievement is important, in this context, academic performance is not considered a determining factor in work readiness. Meanwhile, the internship experience variable with a significance value of 0.021 shows a statistically significant influence on work readiness. Internship experience really helps students feel more prepared to enter the workforce, because internships provide opportunities to gain practical skills and understand the dynamics of the professional world.

Thus, it can be concluded that self-efficacy and internship experience play a significant role in improving students' work readiness, while academic performance does not provide a significant contribution in this context.

F test (simultaneous)

The F test is used to measure the simultaneous or concurrent influence of independent variables, namely self-efficacy (X1), academic performance (X2), and internship experience (X3), on the dependent variable, namely work readiness (Y). The following are the results of the F test:

Table 6: F Test Results (Simultaneous)

Model	Sig.
Regression	.000 ^b

Based on the results of the F test which showed a significance value (p-value) of 0.000, it can be concluded that the independent variables, namely self-efficacy (X1), academic performance (X2), and internship experience (X3), simultaneously have a significant influence on the dependent variable, namely work readiness (Y). A p-value smaller than 0.05 indicates that the combination of these three variables can significantly explain variations in students' work readiness. Thus, the regression model involving self-efficacy, academic performance, and internship experience is proven to be relevant and effective in showing the influence of these variables on work readiness.

Determination Coefficient Test

Aiming to evaluate how much variation in work readiness can be explained by the variables of self-efficacy, academic performance, and internship experience, this analysis uses the R-square value (determination coefficient). The following are the R-square values generated from the regression analysis in this study:

Table 7: Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.483 ^a	.234	.207

Based on the results of the determination coefficient test, the R value of 0.483 indicates that there is a fairly strong positive relationship between the variables of self-efficacy, academic

performance, and internships on students' work readiness. However, this relationship is not classified as very strong, but is in the category of moderate relationships. Furthermore, the R Square value of 0.234 indicates that the model is able to explain around 23.4% of the variation in students' work readiness. This means that most of it, namely 76.6%, is still influenced by other factors outside the variables studied.

3.1. The Influence of Self-Efficacy on the Work Readiness

The results of the study showed that self-efficacy has a significant and positive effect on the work readiness of D4 Civil Engineering students at Surabaya State University, class of 2019-2021. With a t-test significance value of 0.000 and a positive regression coefficient of 0.431, it can be concluded that the higher the level of students' self-efficacy, the better their readiness to face the world of work. Students who have high self-efficacy tend to show greater self-confidence and are able to adapt to various challenges that arise. This belief in their abilities encourages them to be proactive in seeking opportunities, such as participating in relevant internship and training programs, which in turn enriches their knowledge and skills. Thus, educational institutions need to pay attention to the development of self-efficacy as an important aspect in preparing graduates who are ready to compete in the job market. Based on the results of the data obtained, it can be concluded that self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on the work readiness of D4 Civil Engineering students at the State University of Surabaya. This finding is in line with research conducted by Ainaiya and Elvi, who found that self-efficacy also has a positive and significant effect on the work readiness of students at the Faculty of Economics, State University of Padang (Padang et al., 2022). However, this study differs from the results obtained by Qristin et al., which showed that there was no effect of self-efficacy on the work readiness of undergraduate students in Semarang (Violinda, et al., 2023)

3.2. The Influence of Academic Performance on the Work Readiness

The results of the study indicate that academic performance does not have a significant effect on the work readiness of D4 Civil Engineering students at Surabaya State University, class of 2019-2021. Although academic performance is often considered as the main indicator of career ability and potential, the results of the t-test revealed a significance value higher than 0.05, indicating that there is no strong relationship between these two variables. This indicates that although students with good academic grades have strong theoretical knowledge, this does not always align with their readiness to enter the workforce. Other factors, such as interpersonal skills, practical experience through internships, and proactive attitudes, may play a greater role in shaping work readiness. Although academic performance still has its own value, the results of this study emphasize the importance of a more holistic approach in preparing students for the workforce, with attention not only to academic aspects, but also to the development of soft skills and practical experience. The results of the data above show that the academic performance variable does not have a significant effect on work readiness. This result is in line with previous research conducted by Kharisma et al. which showed that there was no positive and significant effect between academic achievement and work readiness (ANDIKA, 2019). However, it is different from the research by Fransisca and Donald which showed that academic

achievement has a significant effect on work readiness (Sihotang, 2019). Thus, although academic performance is an important element in education, this study emphasizes the need to develop other aspects that are more relevant to work readiness so that graduates can compete in an increasingly competitive job market.

3.3. The Influence of Internships on the Work Readiness

The results of the study related to the influence of internships on the work readiness of Civil Engineering D4 students, Surabaya State University, class of 2019-2021 showed a significant relationship between internship experience and work readiness. With a t-test significance value of 0.021, this study indicates that internship experience has a significant effect on students' work readiness. Although there is a negative regression coefficient of -0.122 indicating an unexpected effect, the results of this test confirm that internship experience remains an important factor. Students who undergo internship programs tend to be more prepared to face challenges in the professional world compared to those who do not have such experience, because internships allow them to apply the theories they have learned in real environments (Jordi & Sutabri, 2024). Through internship experience, students not only gain technical skills relevant to their field of study, but also develop essential soft skills, such as communication skills, teamwork, and flexibility in dealing with various situations. Although there is a negative regression coefficient indicating a possible negative impact, this can occur if the internship experience is poorly managed or not relevant to industry needs. Therefore, it is important for educational institutions to ensure that students have access to quality internship programs and provide guidance in choosing the right opportunities. Based on the data results above, it can be seen that internships have a significant effect on students' work readiness. The results obtained are in line with research conducted, (Muhammad et al., 2021) which shows that internship experience has a positive and significant impact on the work readiness of students at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Brawijaya University.

Overall, this study emphasizes that internship experience plays a crucial role in improving students' work readiness, so educational institutions should focus more on developing internship programs as an integral part of the curriculum to prepare competent graduates who are ready to compete in the world of work.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the influence of self-efficacy, academic performance, and internships on the work readiness of D4 Civil Engineering students, Surabaya State University, 2019-2021 intake:

- a. The research findings show that self-efficacy has a positive and significant influence on students' work readiness. This shows that high levels of self-confidence among students contribute to their readiness to face challenges in the world of work.
- b. The results show that academic performance does not have a significant effect on work readiness. This suggests that the relationship between academic achievement and work readiness may not be strong and indirect in the context of this study..

- c. Internship experience has a significant effect on job readiness, although it is possible that inappropriate or less relevant internships can have negative effects. This finding underscores the importance of quality and relevance of internship programs for students in preparing themselves for entering the professional world..
- d. Overall, this study shows that self-efficacy, academic performance, and internship experience have a significant influence on students' work readiness. These three variables interact with each other and contribute significantly to preparing students to enter the workforce, although more attention needs to be paid to the influence of academic performance.

Overall, self-efficacy and internships showed a significant influence on students' work readiness, while academic performance did not have a significant impact. The low R Square value indicates that there are other variables that also influence work readiness, which were not examined in this study.

Reference

- 1) Aksa, A. F. (2023). Program Peningkatan Kemampuan Mahasiswa Menghadapi Dunia Kerja Melalui Kegiatan Magang Di Kantor Imigrasi Dan Koperasi Sangosay Atambua. *Jurnal Umum Pengabdian Masyarakat (JUPEMAS)*, 50–56.
- 2) Aliudin, A. P., & Adi Chandra Damora. (2024). Pengaruh Nilai Tukar Rupiah, Produksi Karet, Harga Internasional Terhadap Volume Ekspor Karet Indonesia 2018-2022. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen (JEKMa)*, 28(6), 27–39.
- 3) ANDIKA, K. F. (2019). Pengaruh keaktifan mahasiswa dalam organisasi dan prestasi belajar terhadap kesiapan kerja mahasiswa pendidikan teknik informatika dan komputer universitas sebelas maret surakarta. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Teknik Dan Kejuruan*, 11(2), 69. <https://doi.org/10.20961/jiptek.v11i2.19570>
- 4) Aprilita, A. (2024). *Strategi pengelolaan sumber daya manusia pada generasi z tantangan dan peluang di era digital untuk meningkatkan kematangan karir.*
- 5) Cahyono, Y. R., & Gunawan, A. (2024). Pentingnya Memiliki Soft Skill Bagi Calon Pekerja Sebagai Keterampilan Kesiapan Kerja. In *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Digital* (Vol. 01).
- 6) Dewi, R. S., Mulyati, Y. F., Pendidikan, M., Inggris, B., Tarbiyah, I., Keguruan, D., Syarif, U., Jakarta, H., & Tangerang, B. (2024). Lulusan Berkompetensi Global Abad 21. *Seminar Nasioanl FITK UIN Jakarta*, 1(1).
- 7) Hulwani, L. Z., & Aliyyah, R. R. (2024). *Pentingnya Prestasi Akademik Bagi Mahasiswa : Persepsi Mahasiswa Universitas Djuanda Bogor* (Vol. 3).
- 8) Irfan, A. M., Sri, A., & Wahyuni, A. (2023). *Global Journal Basic Education Analisis Keterampilan Abad 21 Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja Di Dunia Industri Pada Mahasiswa Jurusan Pendidikan Teknik Mesin Ft Unm Artikel info Abstrak* (Vol. 2). <https://jurnal.sainsglobal.com/index.php/gjp>
- 9) Jordi, R., & Sutabri, T. (2024). Studi Mendalam Tentang Kehadiran Industri Prakerin dan Kompetensi Lokal di Kota Palembang Implikasi Terhadap Eksistensi Program Studi Teknik Informatika. *IJM: Indonesian Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 2(3), 98–105.
- 10) Lestari, E., & Arini, E. (2024). Pengaruh Beban Kerja Dan Manajemen Waktu Terhadap Efektivitas Kerja Karyawan Di Perumda Tirta Hidayah Kota Bengkulu. *Jurnal Fokus Manajemen*, 4(1), 121–128.

- 11) Lucas, N., Lie, C., Noviaty, K., Darmasetiawan, S., & Psi, M. S. (2017). Pengaruh Soft Skill Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja Menghadapi Masyarakat Ekonomi Asean Pada Mahasiswa S1 Fakultas Bisnis Dan Ekonomika Universitas Surabaya. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Universitas Surabaya*, 6(2), 1496–1514.
- 12) Marlinah, L. (2019). Pentingnya Peran Perguruan Tinggi Dalam Mencetak Sdm Yang Berjiwa Inovator Dan Technopreneur Menyongsong Era Society 5.0. *Jurnal IKRA-ITH Ekonomika*, 2(3), 17–25.
- 13) maryam, N. S. (2023). Urgensi pendidikan karakter bagi mahasiswa di era digital. *JPSS: Jurnal Pendidikan Sang Surya*, 9(1), 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.56959>
- 14) Mufidah, A. C. (2017). Hubungan Antara Dukungan Sosial Terhadap Resiliensi Pada Mahasiswa Bidikmisi Dengan Mediasi Efikasi Diri. *Jurnal Sains Psikolog*, 6(2), 68–74.
- 15) Mufidatul, A., Arifah, M. ', & Utami, D. D. (2024). *Rasionalitas Mahasiswa Memilih Magang Dalam Program MISB (Studi Pada Mahasiswa Universitas Negeri Surabaya)* (Vol. 13, Issue 3).
- 16) Muhammad, A., Mustari, I., & Armanu, H. (2021). Pengaruh Pengalaman Magang Dan Minat Kerja Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja (Studi pada Mahasiswa Fakultas Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Universitas Brawijaya). *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa FEB*, 9(2).
- 17) P Sumampouw, P. N., & Mandey, S. L. (n.d.). Pengaruh Efikasi Diri, Prestasi Belajar Dan Perencanaan Karir Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja Mahasiswa Jurusan Manajemen Feb Unsrat The Effect of Self-Efficacy, Learning Achievement and Career Planning on Work Readiness of Students Majoring In Management FEB Unsrat Oleh. In *Januari-Maret* (Vol. 8, Issue 2).
- 18) Padang, U. N., Alfatihah, A., & Rahmi, E. (2022). *Jurnal Ecogen Pengaruh Karakteristik Entrepreneur dan Efikasi Diri Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja Mahasiswa ARTICLE INFO ABSTRACT*. 5(4), 555–567. <https://doi.org/10.24036/jmpe.v5i4.1400>
- 19) Rukiyanto, B. A., Nurzaima, Widyatiningtyas, R., Tambunan, Solisa, E. M., & Marzuki. (2023). Hubungan antara pendidikan karakter dan prestasi akademik mahasiswa perguruan tinggi. *Jurnal Review Pendidikan Dan Pengajaran*, 6(4), 4017–4025.
- 20) Sagala, D., Siregar, D., & Yamin Siregar, M. (2024). Pengaruh Pengetahuan Kewirausahaan dan Efikasi Diri Terhadap Minat Berwirausaha Pada Gen-Z Kabupaten Dair. *Socius: Jurnal Penelitian Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial*, 1(12), 511–521. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12955791>
- 21) Sihotang, F. H. (2019). Pengaruh Prestasi Belajar, Penguasaan Teknologi Informasi Dan Pengalaman Organisasi Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja. *Program Studi Pendidikan Ekonomi FKIP Universitas Kristen Satya Wacana*, 1–6.
- 22) Sriningsih, M., Hatidja, D., & Prang, J. D. (n.d.). *Penanganan multikolinearitas dengan menggunakan analisis regresi komponen utama pada kasus impor beras di provinsi sulut*.
- 23) Telaumbanua, A., & Telaumbanua, A. (2024). Pengaruh Soft Skill Dan Hard Skill Mahasiswa Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja Di Era Revolusi Industri 4.0. *Jurnal Suluh Pendidikan*, 12(2), 126–136.
- 24) Valentina, A. A. F. (n.d.). *Hubungan Pengalaman Magang DU/DI dan Perencanaan Karir Dengan Kesiapan Kerja Mahasiswa Pendidikan Akuntansi*.
- 25) Violinda, Q., Wahyuningsih, S., & Meiriyanti, R. (2023). Pengaruh Career Planning, Self Efficacy dan Adversity Quotient Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja Mahasiswa S1 di Semarang. *Jurnal Aplikasi Bisnis Dan Manajemen*. <https://doi.org/10.17358/jabm.9.2.639>